

Local Government in Malaysia

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

Andrew Harding

Centre for Asian Legal Studies
National University of Singapore

Partners

Eurac Research
Institute for Comparative Federalism
Italy

LMU Munich
Research Center for Public Procurement
Law and Administrative Cooperations
Germany

Autonomous University of Madrid
Institute of Local Law
Spain

Institut für Föderalismus
Institut du Fédéralisme
Institute of Federalism

University of Fribourg
Institute of Federalism
Switzerland

NALAS
Network of Associations of Local
Authorities of South East Europe
France

ximpulse
Ximpulse GmbH
Switzerland

KDZ
Center for Public Administration Research
Austria

Council of Europe
Congress of Local and Regional Authorities
France

Faculty of Political Science
and International Studies
University of Warsaw
University of Warsaw
Institute of Political Science
Poland

ZELS
Association of the Units of Local Self-Government
North Macedonia

University of the Western Cape
Dullah Omar Institute for Constitutional
Law, Governance and Human Rights
South Africa

Addis Ababa University
Center for Federalism and Governance Studies
Ethiopia

UNIVERSIDAD
NACIONAL DE
SAN MARTÍN

Universidad Nacional de General San Martín
School of Politics and Government
Argentina

SALGA
South African Local Government Association
South Africa

जवाहरलाल नेहरू विश्वविद्यालय
Jawaharlal Nehru University
Jawaharlal Nehru University
India

University of Technology Sydney
Institute for Public Policy and Governance
Centre for Local Government
Australia

National University of Singapore
Centre for Asian Legal Studies
Asia Pacific Centre for Environmental Law
Singapore

University of Western Ontario
Centre for Urban Policy and Local Governance
Canada

November 2021

The Country Report on Local Government in Malaysia is a product of the LoGov-project: “Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay”.

The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

LICENSE

CC BY 4.0

INFORMATION

Eurac Research
Viale Druso/Drususallee, 1
39100 Bolzano/Bozen – Italy

logov@eurac.edu
www.logov-rise.eu

SCIENTIFIC COORDINATION

Eurac Research: Karl Kössler

WP 1 – Local Responsibilities and Public Services

LMU Munich: Martin Burgi

WP 2 – Local Financial Arrangements

Universidad Autónoma de Madrid: Francisco Velasco Caballero

WP 3 – Structure of Local Government

University of Fribourg: Eva Maria Belser

WP 4 – Intergovernmental Relations of Local Government

NALAS – Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South East Europe: Elton Stafa

WP 5 – People’s Participation in Local Decision-Making

Ximpulse GmbH: Erika Schläppi

EDITORIAL TEAM

National University of Singapore: Andrew Harding
Eurac Research: Karl Kössler, Theresia Morandell, Caterina Salvo, Annika Kress, Petra Malferttheiner

GRAPHIC DESIGN

Eurac Research: Alessandra Stefanut

COVER PHOTO

Sadie Teper/Unsplash

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 823961.

Contents

1. The System of Local Government in Malaysia.....	1
2.1. Local Responsibilities and Public Services in Malaysia: An Introduction	9
2.2. <i>Planning, Housing Development, and the Ethnic-Preference System</i>	11
3.1. Local Financial Arrangements in Malaysia: An Introduction	15
3.2. <i>Urban Cleansing and Privatisation</i>	21
4.1. The Structure of Local Government in Malaysia: An Introduction	25
4.2. <i>Iskandar Development Region</i>	27
5.1. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Malaysia: An Introduction.....	31
5.2. <i>The SPICE Controversy</i>	35
6.1. People’s Participation in Local Decision-Making in Malaysia: An Introduction	39
6.2. <i>Public Consultation in the Drafting of Structure/Local Plans</i>	46

Structure of Local Government

4.2. Iskandar Development Region

Andrew Harding, *Centre for Asian Legal Studies, National University of Singapore*

Relevance of the Practice

Development has been a major preoccupation since independence in 1957. Typically of Asia's developmental states, of which Malaysia is a good example, centres of autonomy have been the object of persistent, although not wholly successful, attempts to subordinate them to the developmental aims of successive federal governments, as well as marshalling virtually all branches of the state as well as private interests behind the development agenda.⁵⁸ In this process, the federal government has experimented with what one might call the spatial geography element in development by finding ways of using the territory under its ultimate control (noting that land itself is nonetheless a state matter) to spark economic activity. Examples are the creation of the Multimedia Super-Corridor and Cyberjaya as Asia's answer to Silicon Valley, and the moving of the federal government itself to a new capital at Putrajaya in the same area, to the South of Kuala Lumpur, linking with Kuala Lumpur International Airport.⁵⁹ These projects, in an exercise of political power at the federal level, in effect overrode both state and local governments' powers. In addition, the federal government has experimented with growth corridors, growth triangles, special economic zones, development authorities, and development regions. This study examines Iskandar Development Region Authority/ 'Iskandar Malaysia' (IDRA-IM) as an example of how new structures might serve development purposes and potentially alter the nature and ultimately the structure of local government.

Description of the Practice

The federal government established the IDRA-IM in 2007. Its five territories of operation overlap geographically with that of local authorities in the region, mainly the city councils of Johor Bahru (MPJB) and Iskandar Puteri (MPIP). IDRA-IM is located at the very southernmost tip of the entire Eurasian land mass, with Singapore just one kilometre away across the strait that separates it from the State of Johor. The location is strategic as part of a growth triangle between Malaysia, Singapore and Indonesia, although the Indonesian element in this project has proved minor.

IDRA-IM's main purpose is to attract investment into the region by cooperation both between federal, state and local governments, and with other countries, especially Singapore. As a

⁵⁸ Andrew Harding, *The Constitution of Malaysia: A Contextual Analysis* (Hart Publishing 2012) Chapter 2.

⁵⁹ Michael Likosky, *The Silicon Empire: Law, Culture and Commerce* (Routledge 2005).

former Chief Minister of Johor put it, 'be they local or foreign direct investments from all sources including Singapore, it is the [IM] which will have jurisdiction over issues pertaining to investments'.⁶⁰

Technically this statement is incorrect, as legal jurisdiction still lies with the relevant authorities. The practice developed here is that of defining the powers of IDRA-IM (and it is an acknowledged model not just for Malaysia but for the entire Southeast Asian region) as those of advising the state and local government authorities on investment, not usurping their powers.

Under Section 4 of the 2007 act, the objective of IDRA-IM is to 'develop the region into a strong and sustainable metropolis of international standing'. Its precise functions, defined extensively in Section 5, are essentially in brief to develop policies and plans for development, and give advice to the decision-makers. Since it is co-chaired by the Prime Minister and the Chief Minister of Johor, and the Finance Minister is also a member, its influence is obviously very strong, despite its lack of legal powers. The Sultan of Johor also has much influence over its activities and takes a keen interest.⁶¹ The mayors of the city councils sit on IDRA-IM's Advisory Committee, so the local authority also has a strong say in deliberations.

As an official interviewed in one study of IM in 2015 stated:

'We adopt a persuasive strategy because the final decision goes to the local council and the Johor state. Sometimes they have their own plans, and sometimes they have their hands tight [sc. tied] because there is someone bigger behind them, so it is not a forward straight engagement.'⁶²

Assessment of the Practice

The structure indicated fulfils the purposes of bringing resources and expertise to bear on galvanising development in a region of large potential growth, creating a space for policy innovation, for example on climate change,⁶³ while leaving undisturbed the normal process of

⁶⁰ Datuk Abdul Ghani Othman, quoted in Elisabetta Nadalutti, 'To what Extent Does Governance Change because of Sub-Regional Cooperation? The Analysis of Iskandar Malaysia' (2016) 19 *International Relations of the Asia-Pacific* 1. See also Agatino Rizzo and John Glasson, 'Iskandar Malaysia' (2012) 29 *Cities* 417; Elisabetta Nadalutti, 'Regional Integration and Migration in Southeast Asia: The Rise of "Iskandar-Malaysia"' in Leila S Talani and Simon McMahon (eds), *The Handbook of the International Political Economy and Migration* (Edward Elgar 2015) 399.

⁶¹ Nadalutti, 'To what Extent Does Governance Change because of Sub-Regional Cooperation?' 22-5.

⁶² *ibid.* 20. Contrary to the examples of public participation in the drafting of development plans outlined under section 6, on the specific project of the Iskandar Development Region there is no public participation.

⁶³ Jose de Oliveira, 'Intergovernmental Relations for Environmental Governance: Cases of Solid Waste Management and Climate Change in two Malaysian States' (2019) 233 *Journal of Environmental Management* 481.

local government decision-making. The local authorities have of course many areas and many functions lying beyond IDRA-IM's interests.

Although there are acknowledged risks and difficulties to be negotiated, the structure adopted departs from the previous developmental strategy of override to engage with dialogue and consultation and has met with practical success in attracting investment, which was however slower in coming than was anticipated at the outset. Most investment comes from China and Singapore.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Nadalutti E, Regional Integration and Migration in Southeast Asia: The Rise of "Iskandar-Malaysia" in Leila S Talani and Simon McMahon (eds), *The Handbook of the International Political Economy and Migration* (Edward Elgar 2015)

DBS Asian Insights, 'Iskandar Malaysia, a Tale of Two Cities' (DBS Group Research 2013) <https://www.guppyunip.my/SectorBriefing01_IskandarMalaysia.pdf>

Contacts

Local Government and the Changing
Urban-Rural Interplay
www.logov-rise.eu
logov@eurac.edu

This project has received funding from
the European Union's Horizon 2020 re-
search and innovation programme under
grant agreement No 823961.

